

References

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Polarography of Tin(II) in Lactic Acid Media

H. S. MAHANTI* and G. S. DESHMUKH

Analytical Chemistry Division, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-5

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THE literature on the polarographic behaviour of tin (II) in a medium composed of organic acids is scanty. The available references are of Deford¹ and co-workers¹, and Lingane². However, no reference has been found regarding the polarographic study of Sn(II) in lactic acid medium. Polarographic behaviour of tin(II) at dropping mercury electrode using lactic acid as a supporting electrolyte has been investigated in some detail. Tin (II) produces well-defined diffusion controlled irreversible double waves, one anodic and the other cathodic, with $E_{1/2}$ -0.16V and -0.49V (vs SCE) respectively in 0.5M lactic acid (pH~2.1). The effects of variation of pH, Hg-pressure and concentration on the wave have been studied.

All the chemicals used were either E. Merck's guaranteed reagent or BDH reagent grade. Tin content in stannous chloride solution was checked by the classical method³. Gelatin (0.01%) was used as a maximum suppressor.

Polarograms were recorded with a Leeds Northrup Electrochemograph type E. The non-polarizable reference electrode used was a saturated calomel electrode with Agar-KNO₃ bridge. The drop time was maintained at 3.2 sec with the open circuit and the product $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ was 2.098 mg^{2/3}/sec^{1/6}. Damping was kept constantly at 2 and recorder sensitivity at 50 x. The pH of the solutions were measured with a line operated Beckman Zeromatic pH meter. The pH of 0.5M lactic acid solution is 2.1; the pH being varied by means of dilute ammonium hydroxide. All experiments were performed at 25° ± 1°. Thoroughly mixed solution (20 ml) of supporting electrolyte, metal ion solution and gelatin was transferred to 50 ml pyrex beaker and was deoxygenated by pure nitrogen before recording the polarogram.

Tin (II) gives well-defined irreversible double waves, one anodic and the other cathodic with half-wave potentials -0.16V and -0.49V (vs SCE) respectively in 0.5M lactic acid. The cathodic and anodic diffusion currents are approximately equal and it is evident that the cathodic wave results from the reduction of the

stannous-lactate complex to the metal and the anodic wave corresponds to the oxidation of stannous-lactate complex to a stannic-lactate complex. These observations are in close agreement with that of Deford¹ and Lingane². Variation of pH and base electrolyte concentration did not affect the nature of the polarogram and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ was observed. Plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ Vs $E_{1/2}$ are linear but the resulting slopes were not found to be in agreement with theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode reaction at dropping mercury electrode.

A number of polarograms in 0.5M lactic acid (pH ~2.1) with different concentrations of tin (II) were drawn. The diffusion current was measured by extrapolation method. The graph plotted between concentration of tin(II) and the diffusion current gave a straight line and can be used for quantitative estimation of tin. The plot of i_d vs square root of the height of the mercury reservoir was found to be linear and passes through the origin. This proves further the diffusion controlled nature of the wave. The diffusion current constant (I) for the anodic and cathodic wave was calculated from the well-known Ilkovic equation $I = i_d / cm^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ and found to be 2.774 and 2.819 respectively.

For determining the tin content of an unknown solution, its polarogram was recorded under the above-mentioned conditions and the diffusion current thus measured referred to the calibration curve obtained under identical operative conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF TIN(II) IN LACTIC ACID MEDIA

Base electrolyte concn = 0.5M lactic acid + 0.01% gelatin, pH~2.1. Total volume of the solution = 20ml			
Sl. No.	Amount of Sn(II) taken mg	Amount of Sn(II) found mg	Error mg
1.	1.18	1.06	-0.12
2.	0.94	0.94	—
3.	2.37	2.31	-0.06
4.	1.78	1.77	-0.01
5.	2.96	2.91	-0.05

It is apparent that tin (II) produces a well-defined irreversible double wave polarogram in lactic acid medium the height of which varies linearly with tin (II) concentration; the wave can be successfully utilized for the determination of tin.

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